

L'impact des facteurs sociodémographiques et la formation en entrepreneuriat sur l'émergence de l'idée d'entreprendre chez les étudiants marocains

The impact of socio-demographic factors and entrepreneurial education on the emergence of the entrepreneurship idea among Moroccan students

Auteur 1 : Nabil RIZQI,

Auteur 2 : Hajar EL HASSANI.

Nabil RIZQI, (Professor Researcher.)

1 Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Polydisciplinary Faculty of Larache

Hajar EL HASSANI, (Professor Researcher.)

1 Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Polydisciplinary Faculty of Larache

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Abstract

Some statistical patterns have been identified in the course of studying the idea of entrepreneurship among young Moroccan students while focusing on the demographic characteristics that determine the likelihood of becoming an entrepreneur. The elements studied include gender, age, level, and type of education pursued.

The results showed/ that men are more likely to start a business than women (in a ratio of about $\frac{3}{4}$) and that entrepreneurs are generally of a higher educational level compared to the average citizen. However, this stream of research is subject to an important limitation that is common to the personality trait approach since both schools of thought assume that different psychological and demographic characteristics have the same consequences regardless of the context in which the potential entrepreneur is situated.

Yet, being set in an environment that favours the founding of a business and being stimulated by external reasons to start a business can also have an influence on the individual who, with the same characteristics, wouldn't carry out the same actions. To address this topic, the adopted research methodology is of a hypothetico-deductive nature, as it is based on the verification of a range of hypotheses among 300 students with a predominantly entrepreneurial background.

Keywords: Socio-demographic factors, Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial education.

Introduction

The last decades have witnessed loads of radical changes in the majority of countries in the world. Economic development is now largely reliant on small and medium-sized enterprises, that are continuously demonstrating their success by fortifying their competitiveness and strengthening their position in the market (Jovičić-Vuković et al., 2020); moreover, the history of developed countries shows that successful SMEs are a basic pre-requisite for effective economic development, as well as for solving many economic and social issues.

Nowadays, the entrepreneurial phenomenon is of major significance due to its importance in the socio-economic development of countries and its subsequent benefits in terms of job opportunities generating, productivity improvement, innovation, and growth (C. Mirjam van Praag, et H. Versloot, 2007). It's also the new centre of attention of academic researchers as well as public, private and non-governmental actors (Nishantha, 2009) in order to comprehend this multidimensional and complex phenomenon. In fact, a deep comprehension of its multiple facets proves to be more of an urgent must in order to support and encourage the bearers of entrepreneurial desires by providing them with a solid ground that favours development.

To this end, a significant amount of academic research has been conducted to understand the origins of the entrepreneurial process, and more precisely the motives that stimulate people to start their own businesses (Emin, 2004; Krueger & Carsrud, 1993; Maâlej, 2013; Tounés, 2006). It's the idea of entrepreneurship indeed, the motivation of an individual ahead of the process, a process that consists of several phases, ranging from a simple vision to the actual materialisation of the enterprise (Benredjem & Sahut, 2017). Therefore, it is crucial to measure entrepreneurial intention in order to study the factors that enhance or inhibit entrepreneurial potential.

The largest number of empirical studies that have examined the idea of entrepreneurship has been conducted amongst young students (Bourguiba, 2018) in an attempt to analyse the characteristics of students willing to engage in entrepreneurship. However, it is in the sphere of social psychology that researchers have been able to extract the key theoretical foundations used to model the phenomenon of students' entrepreneurial intention.

Thus, the previously conducted studies generated the possibility to assess the influence of psycho-sociological factors on the behaviours targeted. Among these factors, sociodemographic factors have been considered as explanatory and predictive of the desire for entrepreneurship despite the divergence of the results concerning the importance of the explanatory power of these factors and the methods deployed (Tchagang & Tchankam, 2018).

Nevertheless, two types of relationship have been examined by the researchers: a direct impact of socio-demographic factors on the entrepreneurial drive, and an indirect impact whereby socio-demographic factors impact the entrepreneurial drive through entrepreneurial self-efficacy.

In the present paper, we are mainly focusing on the direct impact of socio-demographic factors on the entrepreneurial drive which will allow us to deeply examine the sociodemographic background that likely stimulates the desire of entrepreneurship amongst Moroccan youth, especially students; as for the main research question, it was necessary to ask the following question: how socio-demographic factors can influence the entrepreneurial intention?

The divergence of approaches has resulted in a plethora of various answers, however, and due to the impossibility of being exhaustive, we have selected and focused on the answers that seemed most relevant and reliable to establish a feasible theoretical framework.

The purpose of this article is to determine the specifications and characteristics of the sociodemographic factors included in our survey in order to investigate their impact on the entrepreneurial sphere; hence, we characterise our sample with the following factors: sex, age and nature of training and education received.

For the present paper, we are focusing, most forwardly, on our position regarding the topic of the research; therefore, the article contains a literature review that justifies the hypotheses we carried in our research; we have also proceeded to include an explanation of our vision and methodology chosen to tackle the topic, eventually, we have explained in details the epistemological position chosen: we have opted for the hypothetico-deductive paradigm/approach; and finally, we will proceed to examine and verify or refute the hypothesis previously formed through statistics.

1. Literature review and development of hypotheses:

1.1. Research background and context:

The establishment of a business by young students has become a major topic in recent years, and the origins of this increased interest are diverse; in fact, it draws a particular attention from local, national, and international authorities as it appears to be a strategic solution to market dysfunctions.

The research context is framed by the economic and social realities of Morocco, given that youth entrepreneurship considered as a solution to unemployment amongst graduates. The number of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) created has risen from 612 in 2007 to 93 517 by the end of November 2021; in number, the national economy has generated 230,000 job opportunity between 2020 and 2021, against a loss of 432,000 jobs a year earlier. More than 165,000 new enterprises established in 2019 and an annual average of enterprises establishment of 121,000 during the three pre-pandemic years, according to the High Commissariat of Planning (HCP). One of the main reasons of the low enterprises founding rate is the institutional difficulties encountered by entrepreneurs, meanwhile other difficulties are contextual, and can be summarised in the inadequate educational system which emphasises. The importance of strengthening the managerial skills of young entrepreneurs in Morocco. Moreover, the founding of enterprises in Morocco requires the development of adequate financial services and in order to provide the youth with appropriate support and insightful information, while improving the business atmosphere in Morocco.

1.2. Research hypotheses development

1.2.1. Gender and the idea of entrepreneurship

The phenomena of entrepreneurship have been harvesting major interest in the business literature, being the core of multiple research set in a descriptive theoretical framework.

Recently the tendency to examine the gender area of entrepreneurship is continuously growing and accordingly the aim to define the influence of gender, as a factor, on the desire to launch a business.

While it has been collectively acknowledged through past research in the ninetens that the entrepreneurial nature is archetypically masculine (Bird & Brush, 2002; Tchagang & Tchankam, 2018) and that women are less likely to engage in business launching activities given that they are male-oriented. Researches today and over last thirty years have been multiple to demolish this stereotypical construct, based on the outgrowing equality between the

various demographic groups within societies, not to mention that the growth of women-owned businesses is a reflection of changes in society (Henry et al., 2016).

In our current paper, we discuss gender broadly, based on the fact that it's socially embedded in the entrepreneurship phenomenon, with a particular focus on the socioeconomic context of Morocco. Our aim is to emphasise the male/female entrepreneurship endeavour in order to determine the influence of gender as a factor on entrepreneurial activity in Morocco; however, it is ought to mention that the gender-relative dialogue is underdeveloped in our chosen context. In fact, the discussion of gender has created quite the controversy amongst scholars as whether to equate the term gender to sex, or to refute this equation and highlight the distinction between both terms while accentuating the social construct as a key aspect of "gender"; nonetheless many academics have been using both terms interchangeably to refer to male / female distinction. As for our research we will, indeed, use both terms correspondently to refer to women and men as sociodemographic subjects of our study regardless the conceptualisation and employment of "gender" as an approach, this choice can be justified by our main goal to discuss whether entrepreneurship is gender/sex natured in Morocco or not, no ulterior motives involved.

Up till the moment, limited studies have been conducted within this area to enhance our comprehension of the impact of gender on the process of entrepreneurship; hence, we developed a hypothesis- that will be either confirmed or refuted- in order to explain the correlation between both concepts: gender and entrepreneurship, in Morocco. Nonetheless, it is important to mention that the results of other research have not been conclusive when it comes to detecting significant gender differences in entrepreneurship.

Hypothesis 1: Gender influences the desire for entrepreneurship.

1.2.2. Age and the idea of entrepreneurship

Many scholars have tried to verify the potential impact of age on individuals' entrepreneurial intentions (Ichou & Verheul, 2010); the results of these studies, however, have not been unanimous in the sense that historical, geographical, and social-cultural factors do play a role indeed in determining the relationship between the two factors.

In fact, field studies have revealed a correlation between the age structure of a population and the rate of new business formation (Falcao et al., 2022). This is due to the fact that younger individuals are more likely to venture out than the elderly (Lévesque & Minniti, 2006).

Accordingly, the most common revelation of research on “Grey entrepreneurship”¹ points out that older people are less likely to engage in entrepreneurial action although they have more experience and means to do so (Blanchflower et al., 2001; Curran & Blackburn, 2001). Meanwhile, other scholars have introduced the idea of opportunity/cost of time in order to understand the age-related effect on the idea of entrepreneurship. They argue that older people are less likely to invest time in activities that require a long payback period and are characterised by an uncertain future (Hatak et al., 2015), hence a negative relationship between age and entrepreneurship (Weber & Schaper, 2004).

In fact, these findings are consistent with the contributions of the American psychologist Laura Carstensen's Socio-Emotional Selectivity theory, in which she states: "Older people tend to maximise their social and emotional gains and minimise their social and emotional risks" (Sahinidis et al., 2021).

Hypothesis 2: Age influences the desire for entrepreneurship.

1.2.3. The nature of education and the idea of entrepreneurship

The theoretical frameworks available in the entrepreneurship literature do not demonstrate the role that diverse education can play in entrepreneurship and its impact on the entrepreneurial desire. Among the best-known models is the one developed by Vyakarnam and Handelberg (2005), that emphasises the impact of the resources required for the performance of the entrepreneurial project without emphasising the importance of a diverse educational background.

Within an enterprise, the team members are the main source of wealth, their initial education, previous experience, and areas of expertise are all factors that influence the team's process (Mucchielli. R, 2002). Since the diversity of the educational backgrounds can have a significant influence on the group process, it consequently has an influence on the decision-making process and the resolution of complex problems that the team may encounter during the entrepreneurial process.

Man et al (2002) argue that entrepreneurial skills could be conceptualized as the set of high-level characteristics that represent the entrepreneur's ability to succeed in his or her business; Hence, these skills are reflected in terms of personality traits, abilities and knowledge shaped by experience, education, social status and other demographic factors. In contrast, (Lampel,

¹ The term 'grey', 'senior' or 'third age' entrepreneurship is used to refer to individuals aged 50 and above who intend to become entrepreneurs

2001) states that entrepreneurial skills represent a combination of experience and intuitive comprehension of clients' needs in order to test and develop opportunities, assess fluid and complex situations and sell client-oriented solutions.

The various definitions mentioned imply the identification of knowledge, know-how and skills required for the entrepreneurial process in order to unfold smoothly, all based on a cognitive research perspective that focuses on the contribution of the education quality and form on the entrepreneurial process.

Hypothesis 3: The form of training influences the desire for entrepreneurship

1.2.4. Entrepreneurial education and the idea of entrepreneurship

Besides the importance of financial support, the necessity of entrepreneurial advice and education is an essential contributing factor in the primary entrepreneurial process. In fact, the management techniques in general, the advice and even the education provided for potential entrepreneurs, are what enables them to develop the entrepreneurial skills necessary to carry out their project. However, education and training, whether before or post business creation, are difficult to develop in the Moroccan context and remains rather minimal and marginal.

We can, therefore, plan educational and training programmes that focus only on the idea of entrepreneurship. In other words, we can illustrate the positive role of enterprises, and build a favourable image towards entrepreneurship; Also, it is ought to mention that Moroccan universities have accorded entrepreneurship a major focus in their academic curriculum, aiming to spread an entrepreneurial culture by promoting the role of the entrepreneur in society.

Our present research aims to clarify whether entrepreneurial education is able to stimulate students to see entrepreneurship as a potential career option through expressing their desire to entrepreneurship; since entrepreneurial education, generally speaking, ensures the transmission and development of precise knowledge, skills and techniques. In this context, the aim of entrepreneurial education is to properly train students to think, analyse and act in particular situations and in diverse environments as entrepreneurs (Crozier M & Friedberg E, 1977).

In fact, entrepreneurial education has multiple facets and dimensions as it brings together the theoretical knowledge and skills that an individual acquires during his or her initial training. It actually provides the necessary foundations needed to understand the particularities of a project. Moreover, the entrepreneurial education also incorporates the skills that students develop during specialised entrepreneurial programmes, plus it involves formulating projects and eventually materialising them and bringing them to reality, and the last dimension of

entrepreneurial education is of an experiential nature and takes the form of entrepreneurial skills and behaviours that result from professional experience (Fayolle, A & T. Verstraete, 2005). Within the same context, further authors confirm that entrepreneurial education or business creation courses are crucial to reinforce people's perceptions of their entrepreneurial skills. On the other hand, W.G. DYER asserts that specialised entrepreneurial education can further nurture the confidence that an individual will need in order to materialize their business idea. Up to date, it is not yet clear whether entrepreneurial education is the appropriate form of education that can enhance the entrepreneurial skills of project developers or can at least stimulate their desire for entrepreneurship, hence our fourth hypothesis.

Hypothesis 4 : Entrepreneurial education influences the desire for entrepreneurship.

2. Research Methodology:

For the field study, we are majorly relying on the quantitative approach since it's the approach that will enable us to formulate an empirical investigation- while relying on a representative sample- that will eventually allow us to confirm or refute the validity of the hypotheses we have previously formulated. All while adopting a deductive approach that involves defining precise questions after defining the main concepts of the research, rigorously, and translating the theoretical analysis into hypotheses that can be a subject to test.

As for the hypothetico-deductive approach, we combined it with the quantitative approach in order to examine the explanatory factors and the relationships between the factors that we have previously anticipated; all while keeping in mind that the main purpose is to detect plausible links between the idea/desire for entrepreneurship and explanatory and predictive characters via socio-demographic factors (Sex and Age) AND / OR education (form or nature of education). However, it is ought to mention that the present article is only a small portion of a large scaled empirical study on entrepreneurial intention. It consists of developing multi-scale survey-type measurement instruments, this approach is mainly used in management sciences in the disciplines of HRM and Marketing, it makes it possible to study the aspects of images, notoriety, perceptions, attitudes, beliefs and behaviors. Which makes it a perfect fit for our research objective as it allows us to investigate the attitudes, subjective norms and perceptions of Moroccan individuals on their environment. To be more precise, we have specifically opted for the method of G.A. CHURCHILL (1979), as it's an adapted method inspired by the work of Azzedine TOUNÉS (2012) and those of IGALENS and P. ROUSSEL (2000).

In numbers, our field study is focused on a sample of students from both public and private institutions and in total, we selected 300 valid statements. The responses to our survey were processed through SPSS software. In details, our target group is of 300 students studying in public institutions (OFPPPT Rabat and Taounate, Faculty of Legal, Economic and Social Sciences Rabat, students of HECI Fez and Meknes). The choice of target is justified by the fact that these students are about to make a career debut and have expressed various desires in terms of profession preferences, moreover, they, supposedly, have sufficient cognitive skills and abilities that facilitate their comprehension and understanding thus their capacity to adequately respond to the survey.

Our sample is a simple random sample selected according to probability laws which involves a veritable random draw while giving each element of the population a known, non-zero chance of being selected in order to guarantee all elements equal chance. Hence opting for a simple random sample is more reliable and allows the parameters of the population to be assessed with a certain degree of reliability since it is based on the laws of probability, not to mention that multiple studies have shown that a simple random sample is a good representation for a population.

3. Results and discussions:

The goal of the field study conducted is to test the validity of the hypotheses; in fact, hypothesis testing involves checking the influence of the socio-demographic explanatory factors on the factor to be examined, i.e., entrepreneurship.

Before proceeding to the hypotheses analysis, it is only appropriate to specify the properties of the socio-demographic data collected via the datasheet of the survey, therefore, we will proceed to describe the characteristics of our sample by relying on the following factors: Gender, age and nature/form of education.

3.1. Gender and the idea of entrepreneurship

The gender breakdown indicates that the sample studied is equally composed of men and women, with 50% men and 50% women respectively. Table 1 presents the details of this distribution.

Table N°1: Distribution by Gender

		Value	Headcount	Percentage
Standard Attributes	Position	86		
	Label	<without>		
	Type	Chain		
	Format	A8		
	Measure	Nominal		
	Role	Entry		
Valid Values	W	Woman	150	50,0%
	M	Man	150	50,0%

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

This equal representation is meant to identify the relationship between the idea of / desire for entrepreneurship and question number fourteen included in the survey, named "Project or enterprise idea".

According to Table 2, where gender is combined with the idea of / desire for entrepreneurship. It has been found that the idea of establishing an enterprise is more likely to occur to men compared to women, in numbers 98% of the men have stated that they had an idea of starting a personal project, whereas only 61.3% of women had a similar thought. In total, 79.7% of the sample confirmed that they had the intention/idea of starting their own project/enterprise, compared to only 20.3% that didn't come across a similar idea.

Table N°2: Cross-tabulation «Gender - Project idea»

Gender			Project Idea		Total
			No	Yes	
Women	Headcount		58	92	150
		% Within the same gender	38,7%	61,3%	100,0%
		% Within the project idea	95,1%	38,5%	50,0%
	% Of the total		19,3%	30,7%	50,0%
		Headcount	3	147	150
		% Within the same gender	2,0%	98,0%	100,0%
Men	Headcount		4,9%	61,5%	50,0%
		% Within the project idea	4,9%	61,5%	50,0%
		% Of the total	1,0%	49,0%	50,0%
	Headcount		61	239	300
		% Within the same gender	20,3%	79,7%	100,0%
		% Within the project idea	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
Total	% Of the total	20,3%	79,7%	100,0%	

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

For further evidence on the existence of a relationship between the sociodemographic factor Gender and the examined factor desire for / idea of entrepreneurship, we have proceeded to an eventual Chi-square test that will allow us to evaluate the significance of the relationship between both non-metric factors.

The decision on which test to execute on SPSS is based on the degree of statistical significance, commonly referred to as the “p-value”. According to table 3, the significance (p-value) is less than 0.05. Therefore the test confirms that there is a relationship between gender and the idea of entrepreneurship. In fact, gender has an influence on the idea of entrepreneurship.

Table N°3: Chi2 Test « Gender – Project Idea »

	Value	Ddl	Asymptotic significanc e (bilateral)	Exact Sig. (bilateral)	Exact Sig. (unilateral)
Pearson's Chi²	62,247 ^a	1	0,000		
Correction for continuity^b	60,004	1	0,000		
Likelihood ratio	73,411	1	0,000		
Fisher's exact test				0,000	0,000
N of valid observations	300				
a. 0 cells (0,0%) have a theoretical headcount of less than 5. The minimum theoretical headcount is 30,50.					
b. Calculated only for a 2x2 table.					

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

It is now a matter of determining the strength of the relationship mentioned above, which could be demonstrated by Cramer's V method.

Table N°4: Cramer V« Gender – Project Idea »

	Value	Approximate significance
Nominal per Phi	0,456	0,000
Nominal Cramer V	0,456	0,000
N of valid observations	300	

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

The value of Cramer's V is 0.456, which indicates that the relationship is rather average. The null hypothesis (H0) is refuted, to confirm the dependency between gender and entrepreneurship.

3.2. Age and the idea of entrepreneurship

Among the 300 interviewees, the average age is about 26 years old (25.78 years old). Therefore, our sample is composed of a young population: students or junior employees. Our goal is to know if age influences the idea of entrepreneurship.

Table N°5: The average/mean age of the sample.

	N	Minimu m	Maximum	mean	Standard deviation
AGE	300	18,00	52,00	25,7800	7,13826
Valid N (list)	300				

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

Now we need to verify whether the age average is statistically significant. The one-sample test shows that this average is highly significant with a p-value of 0 and a confidence interval at 5% between 24.969 (i.e., 25 years old) and 26.591 (i.e., 27 years old).

Table N°6: Single Sample test

	Test value = 0					
	T	Ddl	Sig. (bilateral)	Mean difference	Difference confidence interval at 95 %	
					Lower	Higher
AGE	62,553	299	0,000	25,78000	24,9690	26,5910

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

Our goal is to find out whether the age of respondents influences the idea of entrepreneurship via an ANOVA test or one-way analysis of variance. The greater the differences between the group averages observed within the sample, the greater the chance that a relationship exists within the population. The smaller the dispersion in the groups, the more realistic the average within the population. The null hypothesis (H0) is "age doesn't influence the idea of entrepreneurship".

Table N°7 : ANOVA « Age – Entrepreneurial idea »

AGE						
	Sum of squares	Ddl	Medium square	F	Sig.	
Inter-groups	779,094	1	779,094	16,060	0,000	
Intra-groups	14456,386	298	48,511			
Total	15235,480	299				

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

With an F-decision of 16.06 and a significance level of 0.000, the null hypothesis is refuted. There seems to be a relationship between the idea of entrepreneurship and age: the older the respondents are, the more likely they consider entrepreneurship.

Figure N°1: Manifestation of the idea of entrepreneurship according to age

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

The age of individuals who do not show an entrepreneurial intention is only 22.59 years old, i.e., 20.34% of the sample. While 79.66% of our sample has an investment idea with an average of 26.59 years old.

Table N°8 : Cross tabulation « Age – Entrepreneurship »

AGE								
	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard error	95% confidence interval for the mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower bound	Higher bound		
No	61	22,5902	3,88320	0,49719	21,5956	23,5847	18,00	35,00
Yes	239	26,5941	7,54584	0,48810	25,6326	27,5557	18,00	52,00
Total	300	25,7800	7,13826	0,41213	24,9690	26,5910	18,00	52,00

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

In a five-year horizon, a time frame used to predict the entrepreneurial idea of the respondents, the highest average of age is 27.36 years old, this average is around 30 years old. However,

most studies indicate that the average age of business founders is between 30 and 35 years old. In this regard, our sample is close to the empirically valid age range.

Table N°9: Cross-tabulation « Age – Time of project idea concretisation »

AGE								
	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard error	95% confidence interval for the mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower bound	Higher bound		
Less than one year	87	24,6092	6,50287	0,69718	23,2232	25,9951	18,00	49,00
Between 1 and less than 3 years	165	26,0485	7,22361	0,56236	24,9381	27,1589	18,00	52,00
Between 3 and 5 years	33	27,3636	6,85938	1,19407	24,9314	29,7959	19,00	42,00
more than 5 years	14	25,7143	9,93385	2,65493	19,9787	31,4499	18,00	51,00
Total	299	25,7592	7,14111	0,41298	24,9465	26,5719	18,00	52,00

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

3.3. Education and the idea of entrepreneurship

Regarding the nature of education, we distinguish between education in public institutions and private ones. The table shows that 53.7% of respondents had received education in public establishments, compared with 46.3% in private institutions.

Table N°10: Distribution «Nature of education Public - Private»

		Value	Headcount	Percentage
Standard attributes	Position	90		
	Label	<sans>		
	Type	Numeric		
	Format	F8		
	Measure	Nominal		
	Role	Input		
Valid values	0	Public	161	53,7%
	1	Private	139	46,3%

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

The intersection of age and the nature of education reveals that there is a difference in age average according to the nature of education received, namely 27.16 years old for students who have undertaken public education courses, compared to 24.18 years old for individuals who have received a private education course. Moreover, the latter has a greater concentration of students between the ages of 18 and 38.

Table N°11: Cross-tabulation « Nature of education – Age »

AGE								
	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard error	95% confidence interval for the mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower bound	Higher bound		
Public	161	27,1615	8,78913	0,69268	25,7935	28,5295	18,00	52,00
Private	139	24,1799	4,00408	0,33962	23,5083	24,8514	18,00	38,00
Total	300	25,7800	7,13826	0,41213	24,9690	26,5910	18,00	52,00

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

88.5% of individuals who received education in private institutions affirm having an idea for a project; this proportion of our sample is higher than that of respondents who received their education in public institutions, where 72% of those questioned confirmed that they had an idea of a project or business.

Table N°12: Cross-tabulation « Nature of education – Entrepreneurial idea»

Type			Project Idea		Total
			No	Yes	
Public		Headcount	45	116	161
		% In Type	28,0%	72,0%	100,0%
		% In Project_idea	73,8%	48,5%	53,7%
		% Of total	15,0%	38,7%	53,7%
Private		Headcount	16	123	139
		% In Type	11,5%	88,5%	100,0%
		% In Project_idea	26,2%	51,5%	46,3%
		% Of total	5,3%	41,0%	46,3%
Total		Headcount	61	239	300
		% In Type	20,3%	79,7%	100,0%
		% In Project_idea	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
		% Of total	20,3%	79,7%	100,0%

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

At this level, it is important to determine if the nature of education influences the idea of entrepreneurship; for that, we will use the Chi-square (Chi2 Test):

Table N°13: Chi-square test « Type of Education – Project Idea »

	Valur	Ddl	Asymptotic significance (2 sided)	Exact sig (2 sided)	Exact sig (1 sided)
Pearson chi-square	12,446 ^a	1	,000		
Correction for continuity^b	11,451	1	,001		
Likelihood ratio	12,950	1	,000		
Fisher's exact test				,000	,000
Linear-by-linear association	12,404	1	,000		
N of valid observations	300				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have a theoretical headcount of less than 5. The theoretical headcount minimum is 28,26.
b. Calculated only for a 2x2 table.

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

The level of significance is 0.000 is less than 0.05, therefore the test confirms that there is a relationship between the nature of education and the idea of entrepreneurship. Indeed, the nature of education has an influence on the idea of entrepreneurship; however, this influence remains weak according to Cramer's V which is only 0.204.

Table N°14: Cramer's V « Type of education – Project Idea »

		Value	Approximate significance
Nominal per Nominal	Phi	0,209	0,000
	Cramer's V	0,209	0,000
N of valid observations		296	

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

Students who attended private education classes were more likely to express an entrepreneurial desire compared to students who received public education. Indeed, 88.5% of private students reported taking entrepreneurship courses, compared to only 28.1% of public institutions' students.

Table N°15: Cross-tabulation « Nature of education – entrepreneurship courses »

Type			Entpship_courses		Total	
			No	Yes		
Public	Headcount		115	45	160	
		% In Type	71,9%	28,1%	100,0%	
		% In Entpship_courses	87,8%	26,8%	53,5%	
		% Of total	38,5%	15,1%	53,5%	
	Private	Headcount		16	123	139
		% In Type		11,5%	88,5%	100,0%
		% In Entpship_courses		12,2%	73,2%	46,5%
		% Of total		5,4%	41,1%	46,5%
Total	Headcount		131	168	299	
	% In Type		43,8%	56,2%	100,0%	
	% In Entpship_courses		100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	
	% Of total		43,8%	56,2%	100,0%	

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

The more the interviewees attend an entrepreneurship course, the more they tend to have a project idea. These courses are available in private institutions more than public ones.

The Chi-square test confirms this finding with a significance level of 0.000 different from 0.05.

Table N°16: Chi-square « Entrepreneurship courses – Entrepreneurial Idea »

	Value	Ddl	Asymptotic significanc e (2 sided)	Exact sig. (2 sided)	Exact sig. (1 sided)
Pearson chi-square	31,080 ^a	1	0,000		
Correction for continuity^b	29,488	1	0,000		
Likelihood ratio	31,625	1	0,000		
Fisher's exact test				0,000	0,000
Linear-by-linear association	30,976	1	0,000		
N of valid observations	299				
a. 0 cells (0,0%) have a theoretical headcount of less than 5. The minimum theoretical headcount is 26,73.					
b. Calculated only for a 2x2 table.					

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

The value of Cramer's V is 0.322, which indicates that the relationship between entrepreneurship courses and entrepreneurship is rather moderate.

Table N°17 : Cramer's V « Entrepreneurship courses – Project Idea »

		Value	Approximate significance
Nominal per	Phi	,322	0,000
Nominal	Cramer's V	,322	0,000
N of valid observations		299	

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

Our research has attempted to highlight the influence of socio-demographic data such as gender, age, and type of received education on the idea of entrepreneurship. The first results affirm that there is a relationship with variant degrees of influence. Certain statistical regularities have been revealed:

- The idea of entrepreneurship is more prevalent among men than women.
- The idea of entrepreneurship is more important when individuals reach professional maturity (around 26 years old).
- The idea of entrepreneurship is more prevalent among individuals who have taken entrepreneurship focus courses on private institutions rather than public ones.

Table N°18: Socio-demographic data questions: confirmation and strength of the relationship

Questions	Affirmation	Strength of relationship
Gender influences the idea of entrepreneurship	Yes	Average
Age influences the idea of entrepreneurship	Yes	Low
The type of received education influences the idea of entrepreneurship	Yes	Low
Entrepreneurship courses influence the idea of entrepreneurship	Yes	Average

Source: Authors' own processing (Via SPSS)

Conclusion

The research on entrepreneurship continues to be characterised by sociodemographic factors and explained by the educational background of individuals, hence our research methodology leaned toward a quantitative-based analysis with a comparative approach between the different groups studied.

Based on results found, and from an economic and societal point of view, we stress a potential cause of concern in terms of gender distinction as female entrepreneurship should be encouraged and female entry barriers should be more analysed and resolved. On an age-related level, the results have shown a significant reluctance amongst the youngest groups of the population studied. Which could be a ground for a more age focalised future research, and lastly, regarding the educational background aspect, our research results highlight the crucial role that entrepreneurship-focused courses play in enhancing an individual's desire to launch a business, hence the major importance for an upgrade within the educational system to offer more diverse course opportunities in this specific field.

In fact, it's time to walk new roads where entrepreneurship is not only perceived as a solution to unemployment, but rather a pillar of economical and societal growth, an opportunity for innovation to blossom and equality to prosper. We, therefore, suggest that the entry barriers should be minimised and optimally removed. And if we are to study what impacts or influences entrepreneurship, we ought to use the outcome as a primitive knowledge to challenge the reluctance to launch businesses. In other terms, if we want the youth to invest and establish their own enterprises, we are to break the current unclear ground and work more on encouraging and enhancing the desire of entrepreneurship, beyond the social constructs and stereotypes.

The world is shifting, and so is the shape of our societies and economic circumstances; we are not only expected to keep pace but rather innovate instead of regenerate; it is time for entrepreneurial action.

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